

Notas breves

Circulus octoliratus (Carpenter, 1856) and *Phosinella digera* (Laseron, 1956): two new non-indigenous gastropod species for the Mediterranean Sea

Circulus octoliratus (Carpenter, 1856) y *Phosinella digera* (Laseron, 1956): dos nuevas especies de gasterópodos no indígenas del mar Mediterráneo

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INTRODUCTION

The number of non-indigenous species introduced from the Red Sea into the Mediterranean Sea (the so-called “Lessepian invasion”) is continuously increasing (GALIL 2009; TZOMOS *ET AL.* 2012; OVALIS & MIFSUD 2015). Various factors may be affecting this pattern, but the widening of the Suez Canal may be playing a major role although it is probably too early to reach consensus on the magnitude of its impacts (ZENETOS *ET AL.* 2017; STEGER *ET AL.* 2018). In this context, the reporting of new non-indigenous species is an important step towards the description of the invasion process and the quantification of introduction rates. Here we report for the

first time for the Mediterranean Sea two non-indigenous Indo-Pacific gastropods from southern Turkey: *Circulus octoliratus* (Carpenter P.P., 1856) and *Phosinella digera* (Laseron C.F., 1956).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The studied material was collected by the first author in August 2018 in Tasucu, Turkey (36°19'N - 33°53'E), during a scuba dive in 8 metres depth. A sample of bioclastic sediment was collected by hand, rinsed, dried, and sorted out under magnification.

SYSTEMATICS

Order LITTORINIMORPHA Golikov & Starobogatov, 1975
Family VITRINELLIDAE Bush, 1897

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Figure 1. A-C: *Circulus octoliratus*, 1.5 mm; D, E: *Phosinella digera*, 2.5 mm
Figura 1. A-C: *Circulus octoliratus*, 1,5 mm; D, E: *Phosinella digera*, 2,5 mm

Circulus octoliratus (Carpenter 1856) (Figure 1A-C)

Cyclostrema octolirata Carpenter, 1856: 169 [Type locality: Red Sea].

Circulus octoliratus (Carpenter, 1856): JANSSEN, ZUSCHIN & BAAL (2011: 422, pl. 18, fig. 2).

CARPENTER (1856) described *Cyclostrema octolirata* from the Red Sea, but did not figure the species. JANSSEN *ET AL.* (2011) illustrated specimens from Red Sea material present in SMF (Senckenberg Naturmuseum Frankfurt). However, they only briefly discussed but not re-described the species. JANSSEN *ET AL.* (2011) also remarked "A possible

synonym is *C. tornatus* (A. Adams, 1864), described from the Philippines."

We follow these authors on the determination of this taxon as *Circulus octoliratus* (Carpenter, 1856). Our material matches exactly to their figures and sizes. This small species (1-1.5 mm) is widespread in the Indo-Pacific (JANSSEN *ET AL.* 2011).

Family RISSOINIDAE Stimpson, 1865

Phosinella digera (Laseron, 1956) (Fig. 1D-E)

Laseron made a very elaborate description of the species and also provided a figure. JANSSEN *ET AL.* (2011), only recently,

have also recorded this elegant species from the Red Sea. Their material was compared to other rich material from the Red

Sea identified by W. Sleurs as *Rissoina digera*. They figure this species and we also follow their opinion, since our specimens

match exactly with their description and figure. The species has now been transferred to the genus *Phosinella*.

DISCUSSION

These species are likely Lessepsian species, that is, they entered the Mediterranean Sea via the Suez Canal and followed the main counter-clock current along the Levantine Basin coastline. Their actual first introduction may have occurred earlier as detection time lags can be multi-decadal especially for small-sized organisms (ALBANO ET AL. 2018). Moreover, it is not unusual that species first detected in Turkey have been later recorded in Israel: two recent examples are the gastropods *Varicopeza pauxilla* (A. Adams, 1855), first recorded in south-eastern Turkey (ÖZTÜRK ET AL. 2017), and *Viriola* cf. *bayani* Jousseume, 1884, first recorded in Greece (MICALI ET AL. 2017) and western Turkey (STAMOULI ET AL. 2017), and only later in Israel (Steger et al 2018). Such late records in Israel confirm the Lessepsian origin and the

detection bias. The shells we found are complete specimens with fresh appearance. Therefore, these shells likely come from a local living population. However, only multiple findings of empty shells or the location of living populations will unambiguously testify the establishment of these two species in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea (MARCHINI, GALIL & OCCHIPINTI-AMBROGI 2015).

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